

Influence of website quality on Customer satisfaction. Evidence from Textile industry of Hyderabad

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Abstract

The theme of current study is to reduce the conflicts and raise the level of satisfaction among management and employees as well as management and customers. Research was conducted in Pakistan by considering the impact of website quality on consumer satisfaction, by keeping in mind the textile industry of Hyderabad Pakistan. Research shows that how reliability, website design, security and privacy impact on customer satisfaction. The data was based on primary source which involves data collection directly from target population using a structured adopted questionnaire based on customer satisfaction. The sample size was 160. The data was analysed using the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 for windows. Present study considered part A that deals with the demographic factors and Segment B deals with the responses related to the organization based performance. The consequences are accessible in tables forms. This study is quantitative in nature. The recommendations highlighted in this study that top management must provide competitive remuneration to the employees of the organization and need to create career development opportunities and develop a communication network between employees and management of the organization. This study concludes with the future direction of the research. The findings of the research are favorable, that can help the textile industries of Pakistan to make their website more efficient to gain customer satisfaction. Existing study can help organizations to know how to deals with the conflicts and which strategies are followed for rising up the organization performance

Keywords: Customer satisfaction, Textile industries, Website reliability, Website security, Website design

INTRODUCTION

According to Ilbahar, et al (2020), the expanding usage of internet is found very beneficial and necessary for firms so that they can stay competitive and combative for providing customers with a time saving and cheaper way for making purchases. Online shopping is referred as to buy things from source of the internet (Omar, Saadan & Seman 2015). It is very beneficial source for all employees and customers which increase the economy of country, it provides various varieties with ease. Online shopping is good source to increase the business of organization, there are too many benefits such as it is easy to control, there will be more variety and customers can purchase their things according to their wish, there is no any tension of crowd or any dilemmas (Henning et al., 2013).

According to some previous studies, website quality has been generally idealized for online business purposes. As such, there are various studies conducted to study website quality and evaluations. Efforts in research are made to understand the importance of website with regards to customer satisfaction especially in

case of textile Industry of Pakistan. This study tries to test the conceptual model showing impact of website quality on customer satisfaction.

Internet shopping is playing a major role in many customers' lives. And the point of website quality and customer satisfaction driven from the service offered (Alberto, et al., 2020). Employees are always considered as main assets of organization therefore satisfaction of employees are essential for success of organization (sumra shaikh, haseeb shaikh, 2019). Due to the fast online service of websites, there is an increasing tendency in online businesses. Sellers can effectively communicate with both the category of customers and in addition cost of buying is reduced when one who do not have time to go out are investing their money in online stores (Nosrati, L. 2008). This occurrence has been valued by both sides of the bargain eg. consumers and businesses. The people who live in developed countries for them shopping online are fast, inexpensive and further it is more convenient than traditional shopping. Britain ranked no: 1 regarding online shopping having almost two thirds of adults which are their frequent online buyers.

In Pakistan, e-commerce has suddenly promoted and boosted up the e-Marketers, whose responsibility is to gather data and analyze and examine data worldwide, indicates the sales of companies from e commerce that it will reach at the growth of 20.7% in 2019 to \$3.535 trillion worldwide. Asia-Pacific exceeds Latin America to become the leader with 25% growth in market for business to consumer e-commerce sales. Websites such as, Face book and Instagram are social networking which are playing a vital role in the growth of e commerce and hence these sites are capturing huge proportion of online buyers. So, it is very important to know the factors that are necessary to help capture and maintain online buyers (Toor, et al., 2017).

Online shopping evolution took place during the late 90s when the internet is on boom phase. Amazon was the first discovered online store that came into existence by Jeff Bezos. Many physical stores like book stores followed Amazon.com for the purpose of success. Later on, many portals like MSN and yahoo came into existence and offered many services like online shopping platforms and channels, where the customers can purchase much more than just books. Although through the passing years online shopping has made its importance in Pakistan. Furthermore, there are many websites offering online services such as Daraz.pk and kaymu which satisfy the needs and wants of people.

Website quality shows the brilliance of a website, (Hasanov & Khalid 2015) they identified various factors affecting website quality, which are, reliability, security and privacy. In parallel, there are many components of website design that are necessary and will fulfill the demand of customers.

Multiple researches were conduct to survey impact of reliability on online purchasing. It is the most important criteria that must be consider while initiating online purchase decision. Online marketers must assure that the customers already trust the website and its reliability, and how the website fulfills its promises. Reliability is known as the technical performance of the site. Information that is given is up to date and accurate. Information available online should not be different from the information available at brick and mortar store. As the customer trust the website, so, when he orders different things, he expects the website will never create any sort of problem today or in the near future (Potgieter, et al., 2017).

Regarding privacy, customers feel more safe and secure when they know their personal information is in safe hands and will never be misused. Customers feel safe, that their information will never be transferred to the third party without the owner's permission (Rosenthal., et al., 2017).

The optic charm of website, that are together organized, usually made for faster execution are features of a website design such as, navigation, well managed content display and aesthetic appearance. There are many effects that are found attractive in a website of e commerce that helps in engaging the customer frequently and compelling him to shop online again and again. Website features hold a positive impact on online purchase decision. Moreover, informative websites help customers to compare and contrast product and alternatives,

which eventually helps in increasing the customer satisfaction (Hsu, Chang & Chen 2012). Kotler (2000) interpreted satisfaction as any individual feel of utmost pleasure or utmost disappointment which is the result of actual VS perceived. Customer satisfaction is the most common word used in business environment therefore factors related satisfaction of employees increase the performance and boost the level of company (sumra shaikh, haseeb shaikh, 2019).

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main objectives of the study are:

- Does Website reliability have significant impact on Customer satisfaction?
- Does Website security and information privacy have significant impact on Customer satisfaction?
- Does website design have significant impact on Customer satisfaction?

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objectives of the study are:

- To classify the website quality on customer satisfaction.
- To classify the website security and privacy on customer satisfaction.
- To classify the website reliability on customer satisfaction.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Theoretical framework shows that reliability, security and privacy as well as website design, all factors have directly linked with customer satisfaction. When reliability, security and privacy as well as website design will increase then customer satisfaction will also increase but when reliability, security and privacy as well as website design will decreased then customer satisfaction will also decrease.

HYPOTHESIS

H₁: Reliability is significant impact on customer satisfaction.

H₂: Security and privacy is significant impact on customer satisfaction.

H₃: Design is significant impact on customer satisfaction.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT:

• CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Satisfied customers are always the trustworthy customers so it is essential to survey customer satisfaction. It is necessary to overview customer's satisfaction in the direction of any particular online shopping website

because the satisfied customers will always shop more and more from the same brand and similarly make repetitive purchases and give positive feedbacks to others creating a positive word of mouth and this in return gives rise to the company's profit (Tandon et al., 2017).

In today's time, customer satisfaction is the most surveyed topic in marketing field because this plays a very significant and most important part at the environment of competition, just because it helps capture new audience very quickly and effectively and keep on satisfying the already ones. Kotler and Keller (2012, p.128) indicated satisfaction as a person's feeling of most and least satisfaction about a particular product or a service expectation and performance. Oliver (2015) identified customer's fulfillment response by considering the customer satisfaction. It is a level of judgment and feeling as per the customer related to a product or service.

- **SECURITY AND PRIVACY AND ITS IMPACT ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION**

According to Alberto et. al (2020), if you want to develop a successful long term relationship with your customers, trust is an important factor to be considered. Because there are a lot of risks involved in online shopping environment, people are less likely to get engaged in trust with online retailers. If a retailer wants to overcome the trust issue and other factors that affect the positive mind set of customer, they should clearly address those issues and try to overcome them (Feizi and Ronaghi, 2010).

According to Wahab et. al (2011), security and privacy is a forerunner variable. These concerns are mostly used to identify a person's interest and level of satisfaction, for instance, personal information control. Privacy is not only considered in online environment but even in individual's daily life, taking a daily life example, if you are entering to anybody's room without knocking the door it is believed that their privacy is violated. As per the (FTC) The Federal Trade Commission they have been assessing and analyzing the online market place since a huge time and has come up with an issue, that is 'privacy' that internet marketers need to sermonize. Based on the above literature, this is noticed that privacy is an important factor that influences e-businesses and e commerce approval (Deyalage and Kulathunga, 2019).

H1: Security and privacy is significant impact on customer satisfaction.

- **Website Design and its impact on Customer Satisfaction**

Website design represents the way in which the content is organized, arranged and managed in the website. Garrett et al. (2017) noticed that website design is a necessary element that helps keep users involved with the website for long. A clearly designed web site, can facilitate customers to easily and smoothly access the information and use it. It stops increasing product uncertainty and answers various queries regarding products and even lead towards post-purchase satisfaction. Moreover, website design definitely provides more worth to the consumer on basis of knowledge. According to a Boston Consulting Group survey (2015), 41% of online shoppers experienced a failure of transaction and they ceased their use of online shopping website. This concluded that those customers now spend a very less amount of money in online purchase. Therefore, a website design should contribute a vital role in locating information online to the customers.

Winnie (2014) observed that a well executing website is captivating, that users can easily use, build up long term relationship with buyers and sellers, enhancing the users' skills. A good website is easy to access e.g. quality of internet line, timing, speed and loading. If a website is colorful and trendy, the engagement of users with the website is increased because colorful content is a very powerful tool to help satisfy the customers.

Research conducted by Chang et al. (2014) on the hotel's website design in Taiwan, shows that the website design attracts the customers in many ways. Additionally, research conducted by Lin (2010) also signifies that website design has a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction.

H2: Design is significant impact on customer satisfaction.

- **RELIABILITY AND ITS IMPACT ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION**

Reliability has gained considerable attention in the marketing field (Chang et al, 2014,). Since, if trust and reliability are present, a customer is likely to feel more satisfied. Several studies have examined and presented a theoretical framework in which reliability clues to customer satisfaction, which develops customer's purchase intention.

Kumar (2017) analyzed that all social relationships will fail, unable to perform or function properly without presence of trust, assurance and reliability, therefore an online customer expects the website to be reliable. Gul (2014) specifically highlights that, when the customers are extremely satisfied or happy towards a product or service, they are basically putting their trust in it Because, reliability forms a chief connection between the website, and its loyal customers.

According to Manar & Abdullah (2018), trust can also be seen in how the consumers are confident in the transactions they perform. online trust and reliability of a website tells a consumer level of faith towards a website.

As per some empirical researches, reliability is considered as the most necessary facet of e-commerce (Omar et al. 2015). Because it is essential to certify that the customers already trust the organization that it will undertake all those actions it promises. According to him, there are some traits for reliability that are considered necessary and help customer's trust company's consistency.

1. Prompt carriage service.
2. Whole demand service.
3. Company is faithful regarding contribution.
4. Reliable service through internet
5. Fulfilling promises regarding promotion.

H3: Reliability is significant impact on customer satisfaction.

In order to achieve the objective of the study, first, the researchers had to go through the specific determinants that affect online customer satisfaction, like reliability, website design and security.

This was not an easy task because every researcher did examine the area of online customer satisfaction differently.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

- **RESEARCH DESIGN**

This research is designed as quantitative in nature, where the methodology is cross sectional study. The population size in this study was studied only once.

- **DATA SOURCE**

This study is completely based on primary data which involves direct collection of data from the respondents. Here, the objective of the study and research issue is being served by primary data source. The collection of data from the targeted respondents is being done by using a structured adopted questionnaire which is based on customer satisfaction and website quality.

- **POPULATION OF THE STUDY**

To get valid data for this research, respondents with similar traits and characteristics were approached for the collection of data. Because the purpose of this research is to study the impact of website quality on customer satisfaction, the collection of data was done from those who have had experience or shopped once at least once or are at least intending to shop in the near future related to the purchasing of textile products.

- **SAMPLING STRATEGY**

When it comes to primary research, the main component is sampling which helps in determining the total number of respondents that are participating in the research. There are multiple constraints in every research in the form of time, finance, geographic. Hence, in current study, it is very important to work on the convenience sampling strategy, that is part of non-probability, which is why much more consideration is given to the proximity of respondents.

• SAMPLE SIZE

Selecting a sample size is necessary, that helps in achieving the objectives of a study. Studying the entire population is nearly impossible so the multifaceted limitations are kept in consideration. Rule of thumb is used for collecting the data (No of items in questionnaire (6) x 10). Hence, the research has a sample size of 160.

• RESEARCH VARIABLES

The systematic process which describes the relationship between the variables in known as Research, whereas a variable is a concept that can simply have a different quantitative value. A dependent variable is simply the variable that is affected by another variable. On the contrary, independent variable is that which brings changes in another variable (Kothari and Gaurav 2014).

In this study, statistical techniques are used to measure relationship between variables, the table below has both dependent and independent variables of the research.

Table 1. Hypothesis, Variables and Techniques

S. No	Hypothesis	Variables		Techniques
		Independent	Dependent	
1	H1	(Website Quality) Reliability	CS*	Reliability analysis, multiple regression analysis
2	H2	(Website Quality) Security & Privacy	CS*	Reliability analysis, multiple regression analysis
3	H3	(Website Quality) Website Design	CS*	Reliability analysis, multiple regression analysis

*CS= Customer satisfaction

• RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

This research uses questionnaire for data collection. The constructs are borrowed from the previous studies. Data is collected on 5- point likert scale questionnaire from strongly disagree to strongly agree.

Table 2. Layout of Questionnaire

Section	Variables	No of items	Scale	Source
1	Customer Satisfaction	4	Likert Scale	(Laleh, 2008)
2	Website Reliability	4	Likert Scale	(Laleh, 2008) (Saha & Zhao, 2005)
3	Security and Privacy	4	Likert Scale	(Saha & Zhao, 2005)
4	Website Design	4	Likert Scale	(Laleh, 2008)

• INSTRUMENT SELECTION

Construct	Measure	Adopted from
Reliability	1. It is easy to find all kind of information that is needed.	(Laleh 2008)
	2. I get, what I ordered from the site.	
	3. The product is delivered by the time as promised by the company	(Saha & Zhao, 2005)
	4. Bill is generated properly. They do not have any hidden extra charges	
Security and Privacy	5. The website has adequate security features	(Laleh 2008)
	6. I feel safe, with my transaction.	
	7. My account information would not be shared to any third party without my permission	
	8. There is no chance to misuse the personal information	(Saha & Zhao, 2005)
Website Design	9. Textile retailers website provides in depth information of brand.	(Laleh, 2008)
	10. The website dose not waste my time	
	11. It is easy and quick to complete transaction at website	
	12. The website has good color combination and aesthetic appeal	
Customer Satisfaction	13. Textile retailers website are best websites, I prefer these while shopping	(Laleh, 2008)
	14. The website(s) offers all details and features that I require for online shopping.	
	15. I am satisfied with my purchasing from the online websites	
	16. I truly enjoy purchasing online textile products (Shirts, Paints etc).	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION:

Table 3. "By Gender"

	frequency	%
Male	74	46.3
Female	86	53.8
Total	160	100.00

In this research, out of 160 respondents, 74 were male with 46.35% and 86 were female with 53.8%.

Table 4. "By Age Group"

	Frequency	%
20-30	133	83.1
30-40	26	16.3
40-50	1	0.6
Total	160	100.00

Table 4 depicts that in this study out of 160 responses 83% respondents belong to the age of group between 20-30, 16% belong to 30-40 and 1% belong to the age group between 40-50.

SECTION B, ORGANIZATIONAL BASED QUESTIONS

Table. 5 "Which social networking site you use most frequently"?

	Frequency	%
You tube	11	6.9
Instagram	31	19.4
Facebook	118	73.8
Total	160	100.0

Table 5 portrays that in the study out of 160 respondents 74% voted for Facebook, 19% for Instagram and 7% for YouTube. Through Facebook people can interact with each other easily, the expenses of marketing will be lower, organization will know the interest level of their customers, loyalty of brand will increase. The result shows that Face book is an imperative factor which increase the benefits for organization as well as country.

Table. 6 "which most frequent activity do you perform on social networking site"?

	Frequency	%
chatting	42	6.3
Posting comments	31	19.4
Searching new products and services	76	47.5
Making new friends	11	6.9
Total	160	100.00

In this table 6, out of 160 responses 48% of the people search new products and service on the social networking site, 26% people chat, 19% post comments and 7% of population make new friends on social

networking site. Social networking site is very helpful site to increase the knowledge regarding products, which product has good quality, which product has good designing features and which product is sustainable for customers.

Table. 7 ‘‘How often do you visit the social networking site in a day’’?

	Frequency	%
1 time	10	6.3
2 times	9	5.6
3 times	34	21.3
4 times	20	12.5
5 times	17	10.6
5 or more	70	43.8
Total	160	100.0

In table 7, out of 160 responses 44% of the population use social networking site for more than 5 times, 21% uses for 3 times, 12% uses for 4 times and lastly 11% uses for 5 times. The result shows that more customers visit the network, then more customers will be familiar to it and that will boost customers’ knowledge regarding product.

Table.8 ‘‘Do you check what other people post about brands’’?

	Frequency	%
Yes	91	56.9
No	69	43.1
Total	160	100.00

In table 8, 57% respondents of the sample population (160) said that they check what other people post about brands and 43% said that they don’t check. Monitoring is important factor because of check or monitor your brands customers will able to achieve right product at right time.

RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

Table 9. Reliability test

Variables(website quality)	Cronbach’s alpha	Number of items
Customer satisfaction	0.767	4
Reliability	0.65	4
Security and privacy	0.764	4
Website design	0.777	4

In table 9, ‘‘reliability analysis’’ the Cronbach’s Alpha value is used for the final decision about reliability on studied data. On that basis we can check the level of reliability in terms of poor, good or excellent. In our case, Cronbach’s Alpha value for customer satisfaction is 0.767 or 76.7% which is excellent, for reliability it is 0.65 or 65%, for security and privacy it is 0.764 or 76% and lastly for website design it’s 0.777 or

77% for four items each. though we can say that website quality variables and the tool is reliable as its scores are greater than 0.5. Overall result conclude that customer satisfaction is very necessary for organization, if organization wants to increase their profit then their first target is to achieve the customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction increase the reputation of organization that ultimately create positive impact on country.

MULTIPLE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Table 10 of regression test:

Table 10.1 Model summary

Model	R square
1	.152

a. Predictors: (Constant), WD, R, SP

b. Dépendent variable : Customer satisfaction

In the above table 10.1 of model summary, it indicates the relationship between estimated value of dependent variable and studied variables. All mentioned independent variables show the R value in the study 0.152. R value indicates the overall fitness of model also. All factors have positive consequences on customer satisfaction that shows that websites are easily maintained and developed and it will increase the experience among customers through which they will get the knowledge regarding reliability, design and security.

Table 10.2 Anova test

Model	sig
Regression	.000 ^b

Table 10.2 indicate the fitness of model; in our research the value of P is 0.00 which is smaller than 0.05. This P value states that our research model is fit and we can predict the result of dependent variable with regards to independent variables is good and positive.

Table 10.3 Coefficient test

Model	Standardized coefficients beta	p-value	Collinearity statistics VIF
Reliability	0.84	0.029	1.146
Security and privacy	0.170	0.003	1.199
Website design	0.267	0.001	1.104

Dependent variable: CS

A coefficient table 10.3 shows two significant values of beta and sig values or p-values. The value of beta usually tells relationship between independent variable and dependent variable whereas p-value tells the level of significance. we can look in our study all the variable that we have studied are found to be positive and significant as they are less than 0.05. we can also examine that in VIF, all studied variables have the value less than 10 which means our research model has no multicollinearity. Hence, our results are not overly estimated. Results showed that websites are very good source to increase the level of trust among customers as well as improve the conservation. Website increase the level of reliability and security with proper designing features that satisfied the customers’ requirements.

HYPOTHESIS ACCEPTANCE/ REJECTION TABLE

Table 11. Based on the above criteria of *sig.* value and VIF we are able to conclude that:

Hypothesis	p-value	Accepted/rejected
H: there is significant impact of reliability on customer satisfaction	.029	Accepted
H: there is significant impact of security and privacy on customer satisfaction	.003	Accepted
H:there is significant impact of website design on customer satisfaction	.001	Accepted

CONCLUSION

The current study has determined the inspiration of website quality on satisfaction level of customers in textile industry within Hyderabad. This research was completely based on customers' authentic knowledge and involvement of using the website services and how it influences them. Therefore, the research concludes that all 3 independent variables have positive relationship with the dependent variable such as customer satisfaction.

This research has three independent variables, that are website design, privacy and security, and reliability where it is clearly stated that website design has the most significant impact, privacy and security has the second most significant impact on customer satisfaction whereas, reliability has no significant impact on the customer satisfaction. Therefore, the two out of three stated hypothesis of current study are accepted and one is rejected based on the results of the study.

4. Recommendations

Below are the recommended suggestions for future research:

1. Focusing mainly on those customers that weren't satisfied and never returned after purchasing once to provide more precise implications.
2. Companies need to focus on reliability factor, trust need to be built in customers' minds.
3. Companies need to address the issue of higher product differentiation, customer finds greater difference in what ordered and what they get
4. Fear in customers' mind related to security and privacy need to be eliminated for increasing the online buyers and customer retention.

FUTURE RESEARCH

There are many others factors and variables which may have substantial impression on customer satisfaction in online purchase decision. More research can be done to explore the impact of other related variables. Pakistan is amongst top countries where e-commerce is growing rapidly. qualitative research can be a good option for researchers, as new and great insights could be gauged from the multiple individuals to identify what motivated them to choose online shopping and what motivates them for physical shopping.

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